

The Influence of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Employer Branding as a Mediation Variable

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Abstract:- This paper aims to regulate the impact of motivation, organizational culture, and employer branding on employee performance. The research population is all marketing and product department employees at KoinWorks totaling 73 employees, so that the entire population is sampled using saturated sampling techniques. The research method used is quantitative with SEM-PLS. Based on the results of the research analysis, motivation has a significant impact on employee performance; organizational culture has no significant effect on employee performance; employer branding has a significant positive effect on employee performance; motivation has a significant positive effect on employer branding; organizational culture has no significant positive effect on employer branding. Employer Branding does not mediate the effect of motivation on employee performance; Employer Branding does not mediate the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. It is recommended for companies to maintain and maintain a coworking space work system and hold routine bonding activities, in order to increase employee performance.

Keywords:- Motivation, Organizational Culture, Employer Branding, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

All activities carried out with the aim of increasing the company's business and the value of the company are a form of performance. The role of employees can be said to be important in these activities because everything that is done must be related to employees. If an employee has good performance and improves all the time, then that can be an advantage for the company and the job of the company is to keep the employee's performance from decreasing and must remain stable for the sake of business and company

continuity. If all employees do not have high and stable performance, then there will be several influences that will occur both with the company and between employees, including communication with fellow employees is not good, conflicts occur between subordinates and superiors, company income will decrease, to job satisfaction from the employees themselves towards the company.

The effect of the pre-survey on the discussion of employee achievement which was filled in by 25 employees stated that many employees still disagreed regarding the statement of providing work results that did not disappoint superiors, always completing each job on time, using working time to the fullest without doing personal activities, and unable to try to multitask at work. After getting the results of the pre-survey, the researcher also conducted interviews directly with the Human Resources team at KoinWorks. Considering the outcomes of interviews with PIC Human Resources not only obtained information related to employee performance but also obtained information related to employer branding, obtained some information related to employer branding in KoinWorks, the researcher chose to make the variable employer branding a mediating variable.

With the problems above and several factors that influence them, the right media is needed to increase employee engagement, especially in KoinWorks. One medium that can be used to increase employee engagement at KoinWorks is the Employer Branding concept. According to Kunerth & Mosley (2011) quoted from the Journal Leti Arinawati and friends that the employer brand is recognized as a powerful tool to make employees bound in the company.

The following is the Percentage of Employee Performance at Koin Works during the 2020 and 2021 periods which are explained in Table 1.

Table 1 Employee Performance Level at Koin Works

Tingkat Kinerja	2020		2021	
	Jumlah Karyawan	Persentasi	Jumlah Karyawan	Persentasi
Excelent	10	2,1%	25	3,3%
Good	376	78,9%	568	76,7
Need Improvement	74	15,5%	109	14,7%
Under Performance	16	3,5%	38	5,3%
Total	476	100%	740	100%

Based on the secondary data in table 1, it is known that 15.5% of employees still need improvement and 3.5% of employees are underperforming. This shows that the achievement of employee performance levels is not optimal. Therefore, a qualified workforce is an absolute necessity for companies in achieving maximum service to customers. Thus it is necessary to evaluate the factors that influence employee performance in order to achieve company goals. Employer branding factors can play a role in improving employee performance. Research conducted by Aris Setiyani (2019) states that employee branding is a mediating factor in improving employee achievement. Then, paper produced by Nety Laura (2021) states that Employer Branding has a positive effect on employee performance, but is unable to mediate employee performance.

Based on the results of the pre-survey and secondary data that employees have not provided good work results, in terms of timeliness, employees have not been maximized when completing their work, it is always not in accordance with the deadline. In addition, employees also have not used their working time to the fullest because at work many employees are still doing personal activities, and there is still a low number of employees who are able to multitask at work, Employer branding also does not support the involvement of an employee in Koin Works. From the results of secondary data related to employee performance that is not optimal, there are still many employees in the 'need improvement' and 'under performance' categories. There is a gap that the researcher found between the expectations of the company for the performance of its employees and the real conditions in the field that the researchers found.

Through several employer branding activities held by KoinWorks, the performance of existing employees should increase. However, related to the factors that have been explained previously, namely motivation and organizational culture, it can be a factor why employee engagement in Koin Works is quite low. This is also supported by previous research on employee performance. Paper conducted by Rahmat Hidayat (2021) states that motivation has no effect on improving employee performance. In addition, research conducted by Wulan Sari Girsang (2019) states organizational culture has no significant impact on employee performance.

Researchers in recent years have identified various variables that can affect employee performance. These variables include work motivation, organizational culture, compensation, work motivation, organizational climate, work discipline, leadership, career development, job satisfaction, work discipline, training and organizational commitment. Based on these variables, the variables are purified to obtain the three variables that most influence performance. The results of the preliminary survey show that the variables of work motivation, organizational culture, and employer branding are mostly chosen by the respondents. This research will then analyze the effect of work motivation and organizational culture on employee performance with employer branding as a mediating variable.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A. Employee Performance

Georgepoulos called the Path Goal Theory which states that performance is a function of the facilitating process and the inhibiting process.

According to Robbin in Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara (2018) classifies: (1) Quality of work; (2) work quantity; (3) responsibility; (4) cooperation; (5) initiative.

B. Work Motivation

Robbins (2018) defines work motivation as a process that explains the intensity, direction, persistence of an individual to achieve his goals. Intensity relates to how hard a person tries, this is the element that gets the most attention when talking about work motivation.

Veithzal and Basri (2016) classify work motivation in 3 dimensions, namely: (1) need for achievement; (2) the need for affiliation; (3) the need for power. This is supported by previous research which states that increasing work motivation will improve employee performance (Hidayat 2021).

➤ Hypothesis 1:

Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

C. Organizational Culture

According to Robbins and Judge (2018) Organizational culture is a concept, set of beliefs, and working method that each employee adopts. It may affect how employees act, which can set them apart from other firms.

Robbins and Judge (2018) classify organizational culture into 7 characteristics of organizational culture, namely: (1) Innovation and risk-taking; (2) Attention to details; (3) Outcome Orientation; (4) People Orientation; (5) Team Orientation; and (6) Aggressiveness; (7) Stability. This is supported by previous research which states that improving organizational culture will improve employee performance (Girsang 2019).

➤ Hypothesis 2:

Organizational culture has a positive effect on employee performance.

D. Employer Branding

According to Barow and Mosley (2020) employer branding is a package of economic functions as well as psychological benefits provided by the company and identified with the work provided by the company. The main objective of employer branding is employee development which is manifested in the form of training to build a corporate image that cares about the interests and needs of employees.

Rathee and Ritu (2018) classify employer branding in 3 dimensions, namely: (1) Economic value; (2) Development Value and (3) Social Value. This is supported by previous research which states that increasing employer branding will improve employee performance (Ramadhani, 2022).

➤ *Hypothesis 3:*
 Employer branding has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Based on various previous studies, an increase in employer branding can be influenced by an increase in work motivation (Voirin, et.a 2017) and an increase in organizational culture (Keino, et.al 2017).

➤ *Hypothesis 4:*
 Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employer branding.

➤ *Hypothesis 5:*
 Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employer branding.

In addition, several studies have shown that employer branding mediates the effect of work motivation on employee performance (Buttenberg, 2019), employer branding mediates the influence of organizational culture on employee performance (Dilhan, 2017).

➤ *Hypothesis 6:*
 Employer branding mediates work motivation on employee performance.

➤ *Hypothesis 7:*
 Employer branding mediates organizational culture on employee performance.

E. Conceptual Framework

Based on the research background and theoretical studies above, the conceptual framework of this research can be described as follows:

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is an explanatory research with a quantitative approach designed to determine the effect of work motivation and organizational culture on employee performance with employer branding as a mediating variable. The population in this study were all permanent employees from the Marketing Department and also the Product Department, totaling 73 employees. The sampling technique in this study used a saturated sample, where the entire population was sampled. The saturated sample taken was all

KoinWorks employees under the Marketing and Product departments with a total population of 73, including 44 employees in the Marketing department and 29 employees in the Product department.

Data collection was carried out through a questionnaire instrument whose measurements were under the dimensions and indicators of each variable. The data obtained was then processed and analyzed using SEM-PLS (Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square). Each hypothesis will be tested and analyzed through the SmartPLS application.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Profile of the Responden

Respondents in this study were 73 KoinWorks employees under the Marketing and Product department. Respondents consisted of 41.1% male and 58.9% female, 8.2% had a high school education, 4.1% had a D3 education, 76.7% had a Bachelor/Diploma IV education, and 11% had a Bachelor's degree. Based on age distribution, 23.3% were aged 18-25 years, 69.9% were aged 26-35 years, and 6.8% were aged 36-50 years. Based on job position, 60.3% are in the marketing field, and 39.7% are in the product sector.

B. Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Table 2 Outer Model Result Summary

	Motivation	Org Culture	Employer Branding	Employee Perf
MK1	0.836			
MK2	0.904			
MK3	0.881			
MK4	0.842			
MK5	0.741			
MK6	0.890			
MK7	0.839			
MK8	0.812			
MK9	0.812			
MK10	0.861			
MK11	0.875			
MK12	0.896			
MK13	0.756			
MK14	0.814			
MK15	0.764			
BO1		0.803		
BO2		0.789		
BO3		0.801		
BO4		0.841		
BO5		0.856		
BO6		0.865		
BO7		0.824		
BO8		0.817		
BO9		0.765		
BO10		0.814		
BO11		0.840		
BO12		0.831		
BO13		0.836		
BO14		0.774		
EB1			0.834	
EB2			0.784	
EB3			0.858	
EB4			0.853	
EB5			0.820	
EB6			0.862	
EB7			0.851	
EB8			0.824	
EB9			0.780	
KK1				0.813
KK2				0.843
KK3				0.749
KK5				0.821
KK6				0.815
KK10				0.822
KK11				0.831
KK12				0.862

KK13				0.848
KK14				0.878

Table 3 Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Value Results

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Motivation	0.700
Org Culture	0.670
Employer Branding	0.689
Employee Perf	0.687

C. Validity Test

➤ Convergent Validity

Table 2 shows the relationship between the construct and all question items with an outer loading value > 0.70. Thus, all items have met the convergent validity requirements for explanatory research (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 3 shows the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value ≥0.50, meaning that the variation of each variable in the measurement item has met good convergent validity.

➤ Discriminant Validity

Table 4 Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	Budaya Organisasi	Employer Branding	Employee Perf	Work Motivation
Org Culture				
Employer Branding	0.240			
Employee Perf	0.257	0.711		
Motivation	0.344	0.566	0.678	

The results in Table 4 above show that the HTMT values have met the validity criteria, namely all values <0.9 (Hair et al., 2019). That is, the variance shared by each variable is higher for the measurement item when compared to that shared by other variable items. Therefore, the discriminant validity assessment with HTMT is fulfilled.

➤ Realibility Test

The construct reliability test was conducted after the construct validity test, and it was evaluated employing indicators that evaluate the CR construct, which is used to show exceptional dependability, and two criteria: Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach's Alpha (CA). For a construct to be regarded as reliable, Cronbach's Alpha, or the composite reliability value, must be higher than 0.7; nonetheless, 0.6 is still seen as acceptable (Hair et al., 2013).

Table 5 Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Ket.
Motivation	0.969	0.972	Reliabel
Org Culture	0.962	0.966	Reliabel
Employer branding	0.943	0.952	Reliabel
Employee Perf	0.949	0.956	Reliabel

According to table 5, all variables pass the Cronbach's Alpha and composite reliability tests with values greater than 0.6. The four reliability points proposed by Hinton, et al. (2013) are extremely excellent reliability (> 0.90), high reliability (0.70-0.90), moderate reliability (0.50-0.70), and low reliability (low reliability) 0.50. Because it is above 0.9, the dependability in this study falls into the very excellent category.

D. Structural Model (Inner Model)

➤ Coefficient of Determination Testing (R Square)²

Table 6 R-Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employer branding (Y1)	0.286	0.265
Employee Perf (Y2)	0.580	0.562

As shown in the table above, the R-Square value for the variable employer branding is 0.286, meaning that work motivation and organizational culture affect 28.6% of the contribution of employer branding, while other factors account for the remaining 71.4%. The R-Square value for the employee performance variable, as determined by data processing results, is 0.580, which indicates that 58% of the employee performance contribution is influenced by work motivation, organizational culture, and employer branding,

with the remaining 42% being explained by other non-research factors.

➤ Predictive Relevance (Q Square)

Predictive relevance (Q²) for structural models measures how well the observed values are generated. Predictive Relevance (Q²) for structural models measures how well the observed values are generated by the model and also the parameter estimates.

Table 7 Predictive Relevant (Q-Square)

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Motivation (X1)	1095.000	1095.000	
Org Culture (X2)	1022.000	1022.000	
Employer branding (Y1)	657.000	526.545	0.199
Employee Perf (Y2)	730.000	445.956	0.389

According to the predictive relevance calculation (Q²) in Table 6, the employee performance variable (Y2) has a value of 0.389 and the employer branding variable (Y1) has a value of 0.199. These two variables have values larger than 0, hence it is clear that the model has useful predictive value.

supporting the theory, structural equation modeling in a complete model explains whether or not there is a link between latent variables. If the statistical T value exceeds the T table, the hypothesis is said to be accepted. If the P-value is less than 0.05, the hypothesis is either rejected or accepted using a probability value.

E. Hypotesis Test

Structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis using smartPLS is used for hypothesis testing. In addition to

Fig 2 Hypotesis Test

Table 8 Hypotesis Test

Pengaruh	Original Sample (0)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics (JO/STDEV)	P Values	Ket
Motivasi → Kinerja karyawan	0.422	0.180	2.347	0.019	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Budaya Organisasi → Kinerja karyawan	-0.001	0.118	0.007	0.995	Tidak berpengaruh positif dan tidak signifikan
Employer Branding → Kinerja karyawan	0.448	0.165	2.724	0.007	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Motivasi → Employer Branding	0.514	0.145	3.536	0.000	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Budaya Organisasi → Employer Branding	0.054	0.145	0.375	0.708	Tidak berpengaruh positif dan tidak signifikan

Pengaruh	Original Sample (0)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEVI)	P Values	Ket
Motivasi → Employer Branding → Kinerja karyawan	0.231	0.120	1.918	0.056	Tidak berpengaruh positif dan tidak signifikan
Budava Organisasi → Employer Branding → Kinerja karyawan	0.024	0.069	0.345	0.730	Tidak berpengaruh positif dan tidak signifikan

V. DISCUSSION

- **H1:** The impact of employee performance (Y2) on work motivation (X1). It is known that the t-statistic value is $2.347 > 1.98$, the path coefficient value is 0.422, and the P-Values are $0.019 = 0.05$. This indicates that the Employee Performance variable (Y2) is influenced by the Work Motivation variable (X1). Therefore, the study's hypothesis (H1) that "work motivation (X1) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y2)" is accepted. This is consistent with Nelson and Setiawan's research findings from 2019, which showed that motivation in monkeys has a favorable and substantial impact on performance.
- **H2** Employee performance (Y2) is impacted by organizational culture (X2). The path coefficient value is -0.001, the t-statistic value is 0.007 1.98, and the P-Values = $0.995 > = 0.05$ are all well known. This indicates that factors affecting organizational culture do not significantly and favorably affect factors affecting employee performance. As a result, the study's hypotheses (H2) that "organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y2)" are disproved. This is consistent with the findings of Irwan, et al.'s research (2020), which found no relationship between company culture and worker performance.
- **H3** Effect of employer branding (Y1) on Employee Performance (Y2). It is known that the path coefficient value is 0.448, the t-statistic value is $2.724 > 1.98$ and the P-Values = $0.007 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that the employer branding variable has a positive and significant effect on the Employee Performance variable. Thus the hypothesis (H3) in this study which states that "employer branding has a positive and significant effect on employee

performance" is accepted. This is in line with the results of research conducted by Ramadhani (2022) which states that employer branding has an effect on employee performance.

- **H4** Effect of work motivation (X1) on employer branding (Y1). It is known that the path coefficient value is 0.514, the t-statistic value is $3.536 > 1.98$ and the P-Values = $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that the variable influence of work motivation has a positive and significant effect on the variable employer branding. Thus the hypothesis (H4) in this study which states that "work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employer branding" is accepted. This is in line with the results of research conducted by Voirin, et.al (2017) which stated that monkey motivation influences employer branding.
- **H5** The influence of organizational culture (X2) on employer branding (Y1). It is known that the path coefficient value is 0.054, the t-statistic value is 0.375 < 1.98 and the P-Values = $0.708 > \alpha = 0.05$. This means that organizational culture variables have no effect on employer branding variables. Thus the hypothesis (H5) in this study states that "employer branding has a positive and significant effect on employer branding." rejected. This is in line with research by Keino, et.al (2017) which states that organizational culture has no effect on employer branding.
- **H6** There is an effect of work motivation (X1) on employee performance (Y2) which is mediated by employer branding (Y1). It is known that the path coefficient value is 0.231, the t-statistic value is 1.918 < 1.98 and the P-Values = $0.056 > \alpha = 0.05$. This means that the variable work motivation (X1) has no effect on the variable Employee Performance (Y2) which is mediated by employer branding (Y1). Thus the

hypothesis (H6) in this study which states that "work motivation (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the variable Employee Performance (Y2) mediated by employer branding (Y1)" is rejected. This is in line with Buitenberg's research (2019) which states that employer branding can mediate work motivation on employee performance.

- **H7** There is an influence of organizational culture (X2) on Employee Performance (Y2) which is mediated by employer branding (Y1). It is known that the path coefficient value is 0.024, the t-statistic value is 0.345 (< 1.98) and the P-Values = $0.730 > \alpha = 0.05$. This means that the organizational culture variable (X2) has no effect on the Employee Performance variable (Y2) which is mediated by employer branding (Y1). Thus the hypothesis (H7) in this study which states that "organizational culture (X2) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y2) mediated by employer branding (Y1)" is rejected. This is in line with Akuratiya's research (2019) which states that employer branding can mediate organizational culture on employee performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study concludes as follows: work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, organizational culture has no effect on employee performance, employer branding has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employer branding, organizational culture has no effect on employer branding, employer branding has not succeeded in mediating the effect of work motivation on employee performance, employer branding has not succeeded in mediating the influence of organizational culture on employee performance.

This research has several limitations. This study only analyzes work motivation, organizational culture, and employer branding as variables that influence employee performance. In this regard, further research can be conducted on other companies or a wider range of population. Future studies also need to consider using other variables that affect performance, such as leadership, work involvement, work environment, job satisfaction, organizational climate and other variables.

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